

This issue of the newsletter highlights several new DDI developments over the past few months. It is clear that DDI is thriving around the world, as a result of our dedicated community. The annual meeting, to be held in Washington, DC, this year, is an opportunity to reinforce that community spirit and to reenergize us for the year ahead. I look forward to reconnecting with DDI supporters and working together on new projects.

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

IASSIST to Feature Meetings, Sessions on DDI

Several DDI-related events and sessions are scheduled in connection with the upcoming [IASSIST meeting in Washington, DC](#), June 4-8.

- The [Expert Committee](#) will meet on Monday, June 4, 8:30-17:00, in Room 310, Cloyd Heck Marvin Center at George Washington University, Washington, DC.
- The [Steering Committee](#) will meet on Tuesday, June 5, at 9:00-11:30am in the Cabot Room of the Melrose Hotel.
- [DDI Developers](#) will meet on Tuesday, June 5, 9:00-17:00, location TBD.

[Several DDI-related substantive sessions](#) are on the IASSIST program as well.

Dagstuhl Workshops to Take Place in October

Two advanced workshops relating to DDI will be held at [Schloss Dagstuhl, Leibniz Center for Informatics](#), in Wadern, Germany, in 2012.

The first will be a workshop on [“Semantic Statistics for Social,](#)

[Behavioural, and Economic Sciences: Leveraging the DDI Model for the Web,”](#) to be held October 15-19. This is a follow-up to the workshop held on this topic in 2011.

The second workshop, “DDI Lifecycle: Moving Forward (tentative title),” a workshop to

Alerk Amin (standing), Jeremy Iverson (far right), and Wendy Thomas taught a course on DDI Lifecycle in Paris in April.

create a UML model for the DDI specification and expand its coverage, will be held October 22-26. Details will be available soon.

Save the Date~EDDI 2012

The [Norwegian Social Science Data Service \(NSD\)](#) will host EDDI 2012 at their headquarters in Bergen, Norway, on December 3-4, 2012. [More about EDDI...](#)

Save the Date~NADDI 2013!

Patterned after the successful EDDI meetings in Europe, the first ever North American DDI Users Group Meeting will take place at the [University of Kansas](#) in Lawrence, Kansas, April 2-3, 2013. Larry Hoyle, Computer Services Senior Scientist in the KU Institute for Policy and Social Research, has begun organizing the event.

DDI Training Held in Paris

“DDI Lifecycle for Survey Researchers” with instructors Alerk Amin ([CentERdata](#)), Jeremy Iverson ([Colectica](#)), and Wendy Thomas ([University of Minnesota](#)), was held April 2 - 4, 2012, in Paris. This training workshop was organized by

[Réseau Quetelet](#) and [CentERdata](#). The first two days of the workshop focused on researchers and archival use of DDI, while the third day focused on developers.

DDI Training Held at UK Data Archive

On March 27 - 29, 2012, a training session on “DDI-L Training for and at the UK Data Archive” was held with Wendy Thomas and Arofan Gregory providing the instruction. Sponsored by [UK Data Archive, University of Essex](#), the session combined

lecture-style presentations and discussions with hands-on workshops for a specialized technical audience.

New DDI Tools Catalog Now Available

The [DDI Tools Catalog Working Group](#) has deployed a new [catalog](#) that documents DDI tools. The catalog enables users to filter on operating system, DDI version, availability, purpose, license, and name. The group has also developed a tutorial that demonstrates how to submit a description of a new tool.

Name	License	DDI version(s) supported	Description
Colectica Designer	Commercial	3.1	Colectica Designer is a visual DDI metadata editor and survey questionnaire designer. It interacts...
Nesstar Publisher	Freeware	1.x 2.1	Nesstar Publisher is an advanced data management program. It consists of data and metadata...
XML Beans for DDI 3.1	GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL)	3.1	Apache XMLBeans packages for DDI 3.1. XMLBeans is a technology for accessing XML by binding it to...

New DDI Tools Catalog

DDI to Be Presented at Conference in Sydney

[The Eighth International Conference on Social Science Methodology](#) will be held at the University of Sydney, in Sydney, Australia, July 9 - 13, 2012. Joachim Wackerow has organized a session on “The Role of Structured Metadata in Cross-national Surveys.” This session will include the following presentations:

- “Use of DDI Structured Metadata in the Production of Public-use Data Files” ~ Peter Granda ([ICPSR](#) - Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research)
- “Re-using the Structured Metadata of the European Values Study (EVS)” ~ Wolfgang Zenk-Möltgen, Evelyn Brislinger (both [GESIS](#) - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences)
- “Web-based Documentation of Longitudinal Studies” ~ Marcel Hebing, Jan Goebel, Jürgen Schupp (all [SOEP](#) - German Socio-Economic Panel, DIW Berlin)
- “The International Standard for Coding of Education (ISCED) and DDI Lifecycle” - Hilde Orten ([NSD](#) -

Norwegian Social Science Data Services), Joachim Wackerow ([GESIS](#) - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences)

- “Using DDI Lifecycle and XLIFF for Cross-National Surveys” ~ Ingo Barkow ([DIPF](#) - German Institute for International Educational Research)

New DDI Registrar Named

Adam Brown of [Statistics New Zealand](#) has volunteered to serve as the DDI registrar, approving requests for [agency identifiers](#). Pascal Heus of the [Open Data Foundation](#) will act as the backup for this position.

GSIM “Sprint” Meeting Features DDI and SDMX

[GSIM Sprint 2](#), a project to jumpstart the development of GSIM, was hosted by the [Statistical Office of the Republic of Korea](#) (KOSTAT) in Daejeon, Korea, from April 16 - 27, 2012. Joachim Wackerow ([GESIS](#)) and Arofan Gregory and Chris Nelson ([Metadata Technology](#)) and attended the meeting to work on the mapping of GSIM to DDI and SDMX.

[GSIM, or Generic Statistical Information Model](#), is a cornerstone of the strategic vision of the [High Level Group for Strategic Developments in Business Architecture in Statistics](#) to industrialize official statistics. It is intended to provide a common reference model for statistical information to assist organizations when developing statistical information systems and statistical information management frameworks.

SDMX Endorses Work with DDI

Since 2010 representatives from the DDI and SDMX standards have been meeting through a [dialogue process](#) to discuss how the standards can work together. The [DDI Alliance Steering Committee](#) has provided positive feedback on this dialogue and its potential objectives, together with suggestions in regard to the path forward.

Now SDMX has also officially endorsed the dialogue. “I am pleased to confirm that the [SDMX Sponsors](#) welcome the initiative and endorse the continuation of the dialogue to find ways in which SDMX and

DDI can be implemented as complementary standards within the statistical production process” (extract from an e-mail from Ms. Adelheid Burgi-Schmelz, Chair of the SDMX Sponsors Group, February 2012 ~ reproduced with her permission).

DDI Lifecycle 3.2 Draft Development Schemas Now Available

The development schemas leading to DDI-L 3.2 are now available without registration [here](#). Previously, the system required a login and password to access the schemas, but this is no longer required.

The site consists of the following:

trunk

Contains updates which reflect decisions in TIC and close a bug in a development version of the schemas.

tags/3.1

Contains the official 3.1 version of DDI.

branches/proposed3.2

Contains changes as proposed to TIC for discussion.

Each commit is limited to a single bug or bug cluster to facilitate processing. These schemas will change without notice. They should not be used for production level work, but in order to view how specific bugs were handled and to facilitate testing of these new element sets.

New Version of Colectica Reader Available

There is a [new update to Colectica Reader](#), a free DDI 3 viewer for Windows. It can be used to view and validate DDI 3 files. The new version adds support for groups and series of studies, expanded data collection information, and the ability to view rich text formatting from xhtml embedded in DDI.

Metadata Technology Announces DDI Projects

[Metadata Technology](#) North American Inc. has recently entered into new projects:

Collaboration with Statistics Canada on New Data Repository for Research Data Centres. This is a project to centrally administer survey datasets and documentation

and automate their distribution to researchers across the Canada RDC Network.

Advising Australian Bureau of Statistics on New Statistical IT Infrastructure. This project will provide expert assistance in the re-engineering of the [ABS](#) IT infrastructure for statistical production. One of the initiatives of the infrastructure program is to develop a registry-based system of repositories, coordinated through a process-management system.

Development of Data Management Plan Management Tools. This is a collaboration with the Institute of Child Health ([ICH](#)) in the United Kingdom towards the development of new tools to prepare, publish, and maintain data management plans aligned on the DMP Online recommendations.

Providing Support for Data Without Boundaries (DwB) Project. This effort will help design and implement a portal for the search and discovery of datasets held within national archives, statistical offices, and research centers across Europe, facilitating the [DwB](#) goal of equal and easy access to official microdata for the European Research Area.